

SYNTHETIC INVESTIGATIONS IN THE HYDROXY-COUMARIN SERIES.
PART II. SYNTHESIS OF 3:4-DIHYDROXYCOUMARIN

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Syntheses of 3:4-dihydroxycoumarin and 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin have been described.

The 3-alkyl-4-hydroxycoumarins (I, R=alkyl) possess anticoagulant properties, whereas ascorbic acid (II) is strongly coagulant. The physiological properties of the

compound (I, R=OH), which possesses the diolic system- $\text{C}=\overset{\text{HO}}{\text{C}}-\overset{\text{OH}}{\text{C}}-\text{CO}$ - of the ascorbic acid would no doubt prove interesting to investigate. These considerations led to the finding out of a synthetic route for the preparation of 3:4-dihydroxycoumarin (I, R=OH).

Acetylsalicyl chloride has been condensed with acetoxy malonic ester to yield acetylsalicyl-acetoxy malonic ester, which on hydrolysis with caustic soda in methyl alcohol (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 401) in nitrogen atmosphere was expected to yield the compound (I, R=OH), but instead, salicylic acid (m. p. 158°) was obtained.

Next acetylsalicyl chloride was condensed with ethoxymalonic ester to yield acetylsalicyl ethoxymalonic ester, which on hydrolysis with sulphuric acid (p_r 1) yields 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (I, R=OEt). Attempts to de-ethylate (I, R=OEt) with different reagents have failed yielding salicylic acid.

Finally acetoxyacetyl chloride has been condensed with ethyl salicylate in presence of pyridine. Ethyl acetoxyacetylsalicylate undergoes internal Claisen condensation in presence of molecularised sodium or potassium and on acidification with sulphuric acid yields (I, R=OEt), m. p. 226-28° (decomp).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl Acetylsalicyl-acetoxy malonate.—Ethyl acetoxy malonate (10 g.) was slowly dropped on 1.05 g. of molecularised sodium in benzene in the cold and kept for 6 hours when

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all sodium reacted and went into solution. Acetylsalicyl chloride (9 g.) was slowly added to the sodio-salt in the cold. A jelly-like mass was formed which was kept overnight and then refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. It was treated with excess of water, extracted with benzene, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water; the solvent was removed and the residual liquid was distilled at $210^{\circ}/5$ mm. when slight decomposition took place, yield 8.2 g. (Found : C, 56.6; H, 5.23. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 56.8; H, 5.26 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Acetylsalicylacetoxy-malonic Ester.—(a) The ester (5 g.) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (1.5 g. NaOH in 4 c.c. water) in methyl alcohol in nitrogen atmosphere. On cooling sodium salt separated out. The sodium salt was filtered, washed with methyl alcohol, dissolved in water, acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, the solution extracted with ether, ether removed and the residue was kept in a vacuum desiccator. Stars of needle-shaped crystals were obtained. These on recrystallisation from benzene melted at 158° (mixed m. p. with salicylic acid).

(b). The ester (9.8 g.) was similarly hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide (3 g. NaOH in 2.4 c. c. water) in methyl alcohol and the resulting sodium salt was dissolved and acidified in the cold. The solution was kept in the cold for 1 hour and then refluxed over a small flame for 1 hour in nitrogen atmosphere to ensure the elimination of carbon dioxide from the malonic acid system. The solution was cooled and similarly extracted as described in (a). The product was identified as salicylic acid.

(c). The ester (3.1 g.) in methyl alcohol was added to sodium methoxide (0.76 g. sodium) in methyl alcohol. The mixture was cooled in ice and then 0.6 c. c. of water was added and kept overnight in nitrogen atmosphere and then refluxed for 2 hours on a water-bath in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The sodium salt which separated on cooling was treated as described in (a) and (b). The product, however, was found to be salicylic acid.

(d). The ester (2 g.) was refluxed for 6 hours with a mixture of acetic acid (20 c.c.), hydrochloric acid (10 c. c.) and water (2 c. c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. On cooling crystals separated; these were identified as salicylic acid.

(e). The ester (2 g.) was refluxed with sulphuric acid (8%, 25 c. c.). On cooling, crystals separated which were found to be salicylic acid.

(f). The ester (2 g.) was refluxed for 20 hours with sulphuric acid (p_n 1) and the crystals which separated on cooling were identified as salicylic acid. Similar treatment with still more dilute sulphuric acid (viz. of p_n 2 and 3) resulted in the formation of salicylic acid.

Ethyl Ethoxymalonate.—Ethyl chloracetate (57 g.) was condensed with sodium ethoxide (10.6 g. sodium in 150 c. c. alcohol) to form ethoxyacetic ester (40 g.) b. p. 156° .

Ethyl oxalate (41 g.) was added to cooled (freezing mixture) sodium ethoxide (4 g. sodium, 10 c. c. alcohol) in dry benzene and was thoroughly mixed. The ethoxyacetic ester (40 g.) was added drop by drop with shaking and the mixture kept for 48 hours. The reaction product was treated with cold water, the aqueous layer after acidification was worked up. The crude material was pyrolysed at 180° for 4 hours and the residue distilled at $220-225^{\circ}$, yield 16 g.

Ethyl Acetylsalicylethoxymalonate.—Acetylsalicyl chloride (22 g.) was condensed with the sodium salt (2.4 g. sodium) of ethoxymalonic ester (21 g.) in dry benzene. The reaction product on being worked up in the usual way distilled at 180-85°/5 mm. as a semisolid liquid, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 5.98. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 59.0; H, 6.01 per cent).

3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (I, R = OEt).—The above condensation product (15 g.) was refluxed for 32 hours with sulphuric acid (p_s 1, 200 c. c.). On cooling, white crystals separated. These were filtered, dried on a porous plate and crystallised twice from dilute alcohol, m. p. 112° (m. p. of the sample dehydrated by heating in vacuum at 80°, 128°). (Found: C, 63.9; H, 4.90. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.5; H, 4.86 per cent).

The compound is soluble in sodium bicarbonate, but has no reducing properties towards silver nitrate, iodine, indophenol blue etc. It gives no coloration with ferric chloride.

De-ethylation of (I, R = OEt).—(a) 3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (0.5 g.) was refluxed with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1, 11 c. c.) for 12 hours and then extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and the bicarbonate solution was acidified in the cold when white crystals (m. p. 98-111°) were obtained. These on recrystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 111-12° and was identified with (I, R = OEt).

(b) 3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic acid-hydrochloric acid (1:1, 20 c. c.) mixture for 8 hours and was worked up as usual. The product was found to be a mixture of (I, R = OEt) and salicylic acid.

(c) 3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxycoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.) for 4 hours. On cooling, crystals of salicylic acid separated.

Acetoxyacetyl Chloride.—Glycollic acid was prepared by the prolonged refluxing of a solution of potassium chloroacetate in water, then evaporating the solvent to dryness on a water-bath and extracting the dry mass with acetone and removing the solvent first on a water-bath and then in vacuum. Glycollic acid (42 g.) was next converted into acetoxyacetic acid (144-45°/12 mm.) by reacting in the dry state with acetyl chloride first in the cold and then on a water-bath for 1 hour, yield 31 g.

Acetoxyacetic acid (30 g.) was converted into its acid chloride (55-60°/10 mm.) with thionyl chloride (19 c. c.), yield 30 g.

Ethyl Acetoxyacetylsalicylate.—Acetoxyacetyl chloride (24.2 g.) was dropped on a mixture of ethyl salicylate (30 g.) and pyridine (15 g. cooled in a freezing mixture) and kept overnight and then heated on a water-bath for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was diluted with excess of cold water, extracted with benzene, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water, benzene removed and distilled, b. p. 181°/8 mm., yield 35 g. (Found: C, 58.7; H, 5.28. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 58.6; H, 5.26 per cent).

3:4-Dihydroxycoumarin (I, R = OH).—The above condensation product (21 g.) was added to sodium dust (3.2 g.) in dry benzene and refluxed on a water-bath till all sodium went into solution. It was then cooled in ice and excess of ice-water containing calculated quantity of acid was poured into the reaction mixture. It was extracted with benzene and after removal of benzene, the residue was kept in a vacuum desiccator, when crystals

separated. These were dissolved in alcohol, charcoaled and filtered. The alcohol was removed from the solution and the solid left was recrystallised from benzene-alcohol mixture, m. p. 228-28° (decomp). (Found : C, 60.6 ; H, 3.42. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 60.7 ; H, 3.37 per cent).

The above internal condensation can be achieved also with molecularised potassium. The high temperature technique of Link *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2285) for carrying out this reaction was found to give poorer yield.

This compound gives an intense green coloration which vanished rapidly with ferric chloride, a reddish coloration with uranium salts, reduces indophenol blue, silver nitrate, potassium permanganate etc., instantaneously in the cold and in sodium bicarbonate solution it reduces iodine quantitatively.

Thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter and Prof. S. N. Bose for their kind interest and to Dr. D. K. Banerjee for his valuable suggestions and generous help. Thanks are also due to Mr. N. Ghosh for microanalyses of some of the compounds.

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Received June 19, 1946.
